

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Mousa****FIRST NAME: Ahmed****PROGRAM CODE : DGEP****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Professor Kabiru Gulma**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author used the following software: MS. Word

COURSEPACK PERIOD 1

LESSONS LEARNED

1) INTRODUCTION

As a new student who have just joined the Ph.D. in Global Energy Policy, I am looking forward to learning the foundation for effective writing from the ACA-401 course in order to be prepared for my future dissertation. EUCLID's "ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1" is the first document that covers critical guidelines to be followed in several situations, such as citation, rule of thumb, literature review and the difference between American and British English. Period One is essential to improve the writing capabilities, learn a new style and avoid common writing mistakes. The "Basic ACA-401 Tutorial" video provided valuable guidelines to write the response paper. This is my first online degree and since this is a doctorate degree, it is vital to learn from all the available tools as writing response papers will allow me to be better prepared for the other courses. After reading the coursepack for the first period, I am confident that this course will provide the required resources to improve my writing skills and will teach me new writing styles. I have not used the Turabian style before and since EUCLID recommends the use of Turabian style, which is a Chicago style for research, I am looking forward to learning a new style that is recommended for writing dissertation and other research papers (EUCLID 2019, 24).

2) ESSAY WRITING

The first chapter is essay writing which starts by introducing the academic essay and how to start the essay. This section provide valuable instructions and highlights the

basic steps to follow. I have been publishing articles in LinkedIn for years and can relate to the importance of defining the question and analyzing the task early in the essay. “Writing the Essay” section depicts breaking the essay into three parts: the introduction, the body and the conclusion section (EUCLID 2019, 3). This section provided critical tips for effective writing, such as the importance of not rushing into writing an essay from beginning to end in a single session, ensuring logical order, proofreading and ensuring the essay has the three aforementioned sections. I find the last section that discuss questions to ask oneself very informative to ensure the essay meets all guidelines (EUCLID 2019, 4). “*Have I answered the question directly and comprehensively as possible?*” and “*Does the argument make sense? Is it balanced and well researched?*” are among the questions in the section that I find important to keep track when writing my essay.

As an author, I have written four books prior, three of the books are related to the electric power system and the fourth book provides guidelines for preparing for job interviews. I have been an adjunct professor for five years and during my first class, my students asked me to write an electric power system book that will simplify complicated electric theories. I was able to relate to them since when I was an undergraduate student, I had difficulty connecting the theoretical knowledge to the practical world. The most important goal when I started writing the book is to keep it simple and straight to the point. A year after I published the four books, I started a new revision and noticed that there were many grammatical and spelling mistakes in the original copy. I followed similar tips as shown and received positive feedback from the updated revisions (EUCLID 2019, 3).

3) WRITING STYLE

Chapter 3 of EUCLID’s *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1* provides essential rules of thumb for effective writing. Adding the main thesis in the beginning of the paragraph provides clarity for the reader about the thesis’s topic (EUCLID 2019, 14). The coursepack stresses the importance of focused writing and avoiding “*distractions.*” I learned the significance of clear writing by avoiding lengthy paragraphs and shortening the sentences. From my experience writing the four books, clear writing was very essential (EUCLID 2019, 15). Engineering theories and formulas are boring, I learned from my students and other audience that boring text will impact their attention in a negative way and their ability to grasp the knowledge being discussed (ibid.). I strongly agree with the importance of reading out loud; that is how I was able to find most of my published books’ mistakes and proof read the revisions (EUCLID 2019, 16).

I have read several dissertations and papers prior that were based on the APA format; EUCLID recommends the use of Turabian style, which is a Chicago style for research (EUCLID 2019, 24). I have not used the Turabian style before, I plan on following the guidelines in chapter 8, the “*CMS Crib Sheet*”. The Crib Sheet section addresses important writing contents, such as: abbreviations, capitalization, use of compound words, italics and quotation marks, appropriate ways to display numbers, footnotes’ placements, page format setup and headings and tables (EUCLID 2019, 44). Acronyms are extensively

used in the electric power system; this section is very important for my future dissertation to ensure all the guidelines are followed. EUCLID's recommends using the full text when the acronym is introduced the first time and then adding the acronym in parentheses; after the initial introduction, the acronym will suffice throughout the paper (ibid.).

The "Numbers" section offers simple rules to follow regarding when to use the actual number and when to spell out the number. The use of the number varies based on the location, where numbers placed in the beginning of the sentence must be spelled out, while numbers used elsewhere will not be spelled out (EUCLID 2019, 47). Numbers and units are used extensively in the electric power system write-ups, I learned from the "*Numbers & units*" section not to spell out numbers when using symbols, such as the temperature degrees or voltage data. Electric power papers include a large number of calculation; the "*Round numbers*" section provided guidelines for not spelling out exact numbers, since round numbers are not precise, and spelling out rounded numbers only. For example, I will write "The voltage of the line was around two hundred volts" and "The voltage of the line was 202 volts" (ibid.). The Turabian style provides important page format instructions related to the margin size, font size, spacing and adding the page number (EUCLID 2019, 50). I expect to include large number of tables in my paper, and expect to follow the "Tables" section to follow the appropriate guidelines (EUCLID 2019, 52).

4) AMERICAN ENGLISH AND PLAGIARISM

I have been living in the USA for over 20 years, and have been using the American English since then. I have used British English in school until high school. The four books I authored are based on American English. Also, all the articles and other technical papers I wrote were also based on the use of American English. It was reassuring to learn that the use of American English has been growing since the Second World War (EUCLID 2019, 27). I plan on using the standard American English (SAE) for all my courses at EUCLID University. Chapter 6 provided key differences between the two standards and several examples such as different pronunciation for the same spelling, different spelling for the same pronunciation, same terms, although both spelling and pronunciation are different, and words that have different meanings (ibid.). This section showed the importance of indicating the English style that will be used and the importance of not mixing different styles throughout the paper to avoid confusing the reader and maintaining clarity.

I have been writing professional electrical engineering courses for over seven years and understand the importance of ethical writing and avoiding plagiarism. Chapter 2 stressed the significance of avoiding plagiarism and explained what plagiarism is and provided examples (EUCLID 2019, 5). To maintain the writing integrity, it is paramount to provide credit to the authors that will be referenced and to always cite the sources used, which is the best way to avoid plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 6). Plagiarism may result in revenue loss, unethical writing and lack of recognition to the original author(s). This chapter portrayed how to cite others' work and when to use quotations when referencing others (ibid.). This section simplified how to quote long and short paragraphs and explained

paraphrasing other work (EUCLID 2019, 7-8). This section also provided instructions when to avoid citing when stating general information (EUCLID 2019, 9-10).

5) CONCLUSION

I am an electrical engineer and an adjunct professor who enjoys writing and teaching. My aim was always to transform and simplify difficult engineering theories by bridging the gap between theories and the practical work. ACA-401 is my first course in my Ph.D. journey and I have already learned significantly during my first period. This is also my first online degree and I chose EUCLID due to the flexibility and diverse staff. The first coursepack provided valuable guidelines and important points to avoid. Turabian is a new writing style that I must get used to. I am looking forward to completing this course and establishing the required writing effective style to ensure my dissertation is well written and clearly understood by the others.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.